

BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY OF POTATO

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Abstract. *As stated in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-269 dated September 8, 2025, “On additional measures to increase potato production and further develop seed breeding”, potato cultivation is one of the developing branches of agriculture worldwide. Potato is an indispensable product of both daily and festive meals. Today, we, the younger generation, must constantly strive for research, based on the knowledge given by our teachers, in order to ensure food security. In this article, I studied the biological characteristics and cultivation technology of potato.*

Keywords: *chile, phylogenesis, Latona, Fresco, Red Scarlett, Aladdin, Arinda, Arnova, Mondial, Diamant, Picasso, shelf, Condor, Marfona, Romano.*

Introduction. Potato is a plant of temperate climate; however, due to its plasticity (adaptability), it is cultivated in various soil and climatic conditions, providing consistently abundant and high-quality yields. During its growth and development, the potato plant passes through the phases of germination, budding, flowering, leaf yellowing, and maturation. The entire ontogeny of the plant can be conventionally divided into three periods:

1. **From germination to flowering.** During this stage, stems grow and develop intensively, while tuber formation begins slightly.
2. **From flowering to leaf yellowing.** This stage is characterized by the most intensive growth and formation of tubers.
3. **From leaf yellowing and natural withering to tuber ripening.** In this period, tuber growth continues, though at a slower rate compared to the second stage.

The duration of these periods depends on the vegetation period of the varieties: in early-ripening varieties, the stage from germination to flowering lasts 25–35 days, while in mid- and late-ripening varieties it takes 40–45 days. The second stage, from flowering to leaf yellowing, lasts 25–35 days in early and mid-ripening varieties, and 43–50 days in mid-late varieties. The third stage, from leaf yellowing to tuber ripening, takes 20–25 days in early-ripening varieties, and 30–35 days in late-ripening ones. The most important period is the second stage, during which 65–75% of the tuber yield is formed.

The homeland of the potato is the coastal regions of Chile, where the climate is mild, cool, and humid. The soils are rich in potassium, and tuber formation occurs under conditions of abundant precipitation (more than 300 mm), high relative air humidity (over 75%), moderate average daily temperatures (10–15°C), and long-day photoperiods (12–15 hours). Therefore, in the course of its phylogenesis, the potato plant has adapted to low temperatures, high humidity, and long daylight conditions. At present, nearly 377 million tons of potatoes are cultivated annually in 156 countries worldwide.

Potato is a crop that prefers relatively low temperatures. Sprouting and greening of tubers begin when the temperature rises above 5–6°C. For rapid root formation of emerging and newly sprouted plants, sowing is carried out when the temperature reaches around 7°C. At temperatures of 18–20°C, plants emerge quickly. If un-sprouted seed tubers are planted, emergence occurs 6–11 days later. A decrease in temperature to 10–12°C from sowing to emergence delays sprouting by 5–6 days. For sprouting, seed tubers require a sum of effective temperatures of 240–3000°C. During the growing season, the required average sum of effective temperatures (above 10°C) is 1000–1200°C for early-maturing varieties, 1200–1400°C for mid-maturing varieties, and 1400–1600°C for late-maturing varieties.

Potato is a crop demanding in terms of soil nutrients. This is linked to its biological characteristics and the weak development of its extensive biomass. On average, every 100 centners (10 tons) of potato yield removes 50 kg of nitrogen, 20 kg of phosphorus, and 90 kg of potassium from the soil. In terms of nutrient removal, potato surpasses most crops, except for beet and some industrial and vegetable crops. The demand for nutrients varies depending on soil and climatic conditions, level of agrotechnology, soil fertility, and variety. Unlike many other crops, in the early stages of development, the potato plant satisfies its nutrient needs from the seed mother tuber. Even after the plant has sprouted and sufficiently developed its root system, it continues to use nutrients from the seed tuber.

Potato plants are highly demanding with respect to the main nutrients. For potato cultivation, it is recommended to apply per 100 m² of land (one sotik) in pure form: 2.2 kg of nitrogen, 1.7 kg of phosphorus, and 1.1 kg of potassium.

Recommended Varieties for Potato Cultivation: In the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 63 potato varieties are included. The most widely cultivated are as follows:

Early-maturing varieties: Latona, Fresco, Red Scarlett;

Medium-early varieties: Condor, Marfona, Romano, Kuroda, Sante, Diera;

Mid-season varieties: Toyimli, Umid, Kok Saroy, Serkhosil, Aladdin, Arinda, Arnova;

Medium-late varieties: Akrob, Mondial, Diamant, Picasso, and others.

To increase yield, improve quality, and ensure early maturity, sprouted tubers should be used for planting. Planting sprouted tubers in spring increases yield by 12–15% and ensures harvest 10–15 days earlier compared to unsprouted tubers. Locally prepared seed potatoes are

placed in sprouting rooms 30–35 days before planting, while imported seed potatoes are placed 20–25 days earlier. The sprouting room should provide light and maintain a temperature of 18–22°C.

Seed tubers are sorted by size (40–60 g, 60–80 g, 80–100 g) and placed in 2–3 layers on floors or racks (shelves), or into boxes of 12–25 kg. When hand-planting with a hoe and covering the sprouts with soil, tubers with green shoots grown up to 3–4 cm can be planted. Tubers weighing more than 100 g are divided into two or three pieces before spring planting.

Spring planting: Southern regions: February 15 – March 1; Central regions: February 25 – March 10; Northern regions: March 10–20.

Summer planting: Southern regions: early varieties July 10–20, mid-season varieties June 5–20, late varieties June 20–30; Central regions: early varieties July 10–20, mid-season varieties June 10–30, late varieties June 10–20; Northern regions: early varieties June 20–30, mid-season varieties June 15–25, late varieties June 5–10.

Seed tubers are planted at a depth of 5–8 cm. For every 100 m² (one sotik) of land, 30–35 kg of seed tubers weighing 50–70 g each are used. Planting is carried out manually with a hoe on pre-prepared fields. The planting scheme is 70×30 cm or 90×25 cm.

The field is irrigated 1–2 times before full emergence of seedlings, depending on soil and weather conditions. As irrigation stimulates rapid weed growth, 4–6 days after watering, hoeing between rows and ridges should be performed. About 20–25 days after emergence, the first comprehensive cultivation is carried out. Row spacing is loosened to a depth of 15–16 cm, leaving a 10–12 cm protection zone from plants. Plants are then lightly hoed and weeds removed. After this, nitrogen fertilizer (50%) is applied and followed by irrigation. The second comprehensive cultivation is performed 25–28 days after the first, or at the budding stage.

When potatoes are planted in spring, the growing season coincides with cool weather and moist soils, while the tuber-formation period coincides with the onset of hot summer weather. Therefore, during tuber formation, early potatoes require irrigation every 5–6 days, at a rate of 4–4.5 m³ per 100 m² of land. Late potatoes are irrigated every 8–10 days. Irrigation is stopped 2–3 weeks before harvest. Selecting seed tubers by size, shape, and other traits is an important measure for increasing yields. When Colorado potato beetles first appear, they should be collected manually. Once beetles begin to reproduce and lay eggs, chemical control is recommended. For 1000 m² (10 sotik) of potato field, the following pesticides may be used: Karate 5% EC – 10 ml; Confidor 20% EC – 5 ml; Mospilan 20% SP – 20–25 ml; Sumic Alpha 5% EC – 50 ml

These are diluted in 60–70 liters of water and sprayed evenly across the field. Potato tubers are formed at a depth of 25–30 cm, so they must be dug out deeply with a hoe. At this stage, the soil should be moist to ensure that tubers are harvested without damage. The scientific system of crop rotation—alternating vegetables, melons, potatoes, and other crops along fields and roads—is known as crop rotation. There are three main types of crop rotation: field, fodder (near farms), and special rotations. Special crop rotations are designed for cultivating vegetables, melons, potatoes, tobacco, rice, hemp, and similar crops.

In vegetable-growing farms, crop rotation is a fundamental indicator of the farming system and culture, and one of the leading factors for obtaining high yields of vegetable, melon, and potato crops. Proper organization of crop rotation must take into account soil and climatic conditions, water availability, production contracts, specialization, economic indicators, and other factors. Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, alfalfa (lucerne) holds primary importance in all crop rotation schemes. As a crop that improves soil fertility, enriches it with organic matter and nitrogen, lowers

groundwater levels, and prevents salinization, alfalfa plays a crucial ameliorative role. Therefore, alfalfa is an essential component of recommended crop rotations in farms.

Recently, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan has recommended an eight-field crop rotation system with alfalfa cultivated for three years. This system is also applied in vegetable, melon, and potato rotations. For potato cultivation, the 3:3:3:1:1 rotation scheme has been considered optimal: 27% fodder crops, three fields for potatoes and two for repeated crops (46%), one field for vegetables (18%), and one for melons (9%).

Conclusion

In vegetable farming, the use of repeated, intermediate, companion, and green manure (sideral) crops is one of the main factors of intensification. Expanding repeated sowings is one of the most important reserves for increasing potato production. As K.A. Timiryazev emphasized: *“Each sunny day lost without use in meadows, fields, and forests is an irretrievable wealth.”* Repeated cropping is, therefore, an effective method of utilizing solar energy in potato cultivation, allowing 2–3 harvests per unit of land.

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